

We need a food system transformation – in the face of the Ukraine war, now more than ever

The Ukraine crisis exposes the fact that our current ways of producing and consuming food are unsustainable and unjust. In response, we should reinforce – and not abandon – the transformation towards a healthy, just, and environmentally-friendly food system. We need comprehensive solutions that bring relief in the short term and at the same time avert the existential threat our food system poses to the health of people and the planet.

Russia's invasion of Ukraine has created a humanitarian catastrophe, while simultaneously disrupting global energy systems and the world's agricultural markets. Ukraine and Russia are major global producers of wheat, maize, and oilseeds as well as fertilizer and fuel. Exports are likely to be severely disrupted due to the war. The Middle East and Africa are highly dependent on imported grain from the area and will be most affected. Soaring grain prices could push millions of people in these regions into poverty and hunger. As an immediate reaction, policy-makers should ensure open agricultural trade flows and adequate financial support for international food aid programmes.

The anticipated shocks to agricultural markets have also prompted short-sighted suggestions like abandoning sustainable agricultural practices that form part of the EU's Farm2Fork strategy, and increasing Europe's grain production capacities, partly to secure animal feed supply. These measures would not move us towards but further away from a reliable food system that is resilient to future shocks, and delivers healthy and sustainable diets.

Transforming today's food systems to ensure food security

Global food insecurity has its origin not in a shortage of supply, but in high economic inequalities and maldistribution. Today's global food production is more than sufficient to feed an even higher world population. However, grains are fed to animals, used as biofuels, or wasted rather than supplied to those with limited financial means¹.

Contrary to what ongoing discussions might imply, European food security is not under threat from the Ukraine crisis. Rather, Europe is threatened by a long-standing crisis of unhealthy diets with consumption of refined grains and animal products markedly above the recommendations of national dietary guidelines and those for healthy and sustainable diets².

Here we propose three levers for coping with the short-term shocks to the food system while also ensuring human health and long-term sustainable development.

1. Accelerate the shift towards healthier diets with less animal products in Europe (and other high-income countries). A shift towards higher human consumption of legumes, vegetables and fruits, and less animal products in Europe could substantially alleviate pressure on global grain supplies. One-third of global calories are currently used to feed animals³ and more than three-quarters of agricultural land are used to produce

¹Berners-Lee et al. (2018). Current global food production is sufficient to meet human nutritional needs in 2050 provided there is radical societal adaptation. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene*, 6, 52. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.310>; Cassidy et al. (2013). Redefining agricultural yields: from tonnes to people nourished per hectare. *Environmental Research Letters*, 8(3), 034015. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/8/3/034015>

²Willett et al. (2019). Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT–Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems. *The Lancet*, 393(10170), 447–492. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31788-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31788-4); Springmann et al. (2020). The healthiness and sustainability of national and global food based dietary guidelines: modelling study. *BMJ*, 370, m2322. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m2322>

³Cassidy et al. (2013).

animal-source foods⁴. Based on FAO data, we estimate that reducing the EU's use of grains to feed livestock by about one-third could compensate for the collapse of Ukrainian exports of grains and oilseeds⁵.

Concurrent reductions in the consumption and production of animal-source foods would lead to a more balanced food and agricultural system in line with health and environmental targets⁶. Drastically reducing consumption of animal-source foods is a prerequisite for limiting global warming to well below 2°C⁷, halting the continuous destruction and pollution of natural habitats, and thus stopping agriculture's transgression of planetary boundaries⁸. Furthermore, a shift towards predominantly plant-based diets could prevent 11 million premature deaths each year and substantially lower the global burden of disease⁹.

Conversely, political efforts to allocate further land to feed production with the aim of stabilizing livestock capacities within the current crisis are counterproductive to global food security. These efforts increase the feed-food competition and delay the transformation towards more sustainable food production.

2. Increase production of legumes and strengthen Farm2Fork. European agriculture heavily depends on energy-intensive nitrogen fertilizers. Supplies are currently interrupted as Russia is one of the world's largest producers of fertilizers and natural gas. The Farm2Fork strategy, which aims at halving nitrogen surplus and expanding organic agriculture on 25% of the land, would largely reduce this import dependency. Increasing diversity in crop rotations by including nitrogen-fixing legumes could replace synthetic fertilizer by biological fixation¹⁰. Improving nitrogen use efficiency by better dosing and timing of synthetic and organic fertilizers would further reduce imports, and would also result in enormous benefits to climate, air quality, and water quality. In addition, implementing the Farm2Fork strategy rapidly would improve soil quality and strengthen biodiversity in agricultural landscapes, thereby ensuring long-term food security through preserving ecosystem services.

Political efforts to abandon the sustainability targets of the Farm2Fork strategy (including greenhouse gas emission reduction, reduction of nitrogen fertilizer and pesticide use, and protection of fallow land for biodiversity) do not shield us from the current crisis, they rather worsen it and make the crisis permanent. Global warming and ecosystem decline are already affecting crop yields and livelihoods worldwide, a situation that will substantially deteriorate in the absence of ambitious mitigation strategies¹¹.

3. Reduce the amount of food waste. According to our calculations, the amount of wheat wasted in the EU is approximately half the amount of Ukraine's wheat exports and a quarter of other grain exports¹². Efforts to reduce food waste along the value chains from retailers to

⁴Poore et al. (2018). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. *Science*, 360(6392), 987–992. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag0216>

⁵According to FAOSTAT, Ukrainian exports of grains amounted to 57 Mt in 2019, whilst 160 Mt were used as feed in the EU (for the EU, EFTA and UK, the combined value was 175 Mt).

⁶Willett et al. (2019); Springmann et al. (2020)

⁷Clark et al. (2020). Global food system emissions could preclude achieving the 1.5° and 2°C climate change targets. *Science*, 370(6517), 705–708.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba7357>

⁸Springmann et al. (2018a). Options for keeping the food system within environmental limits. *Nature*, 562(7728), 519–525. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0594-0>;

Soergel et al. (2021). A sustainable development pathway for climate action within the UN 2030 Agenda. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(8), 656–664.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-01098-3>

⁹Willett et al. (2019); Afshin et al. (2019). Health effects of dietary risks in 195 countries, 1990–2017: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *The Lancet*, 393(10184), 1958–1972. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(19\)30041-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(19)30041-8);

Springmann et al. (2018b). Health and nutritional aspects of sustainable diet strategies and their association with environmental impacts: A global modelling analysis with country-level detail. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 2(10), e451–e461.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(18\)30206-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(18)30206-7)

¹⁰Drinkwater et al. 1998). Legume-based cropping systems have reduced carbon and nitrogen losses. *Nature*, 396(6708), 262–265. <https://doi.org/10.1038/24376>

¹¹IPCC, 2022: *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability*. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Pörtner et al. (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press. In Press.

¹²According to the FAO, 25% of grains in the EU are wasted in households. We combined this with estimates of EU's demand for wheat, which according to FAOSTAT was 47 Mt in 2019, and compared it to Ukrainian wheat exports, which according to FAOSTAT was 21 Mt in 2019.

private homes could thus reduce short-term pressures on global markets. Food waste does not only contribute to the maldistribution of food supplies, it is also responsible for a large share of our food system's environmental footprint, as 30% of food produced is wasted at different stages of production and consumption¹³. Halving the amount of food waste worldwide by 2030 is therefore also an integral part to align the food system with the Sustainable Development Goals and stay within planetary boundaries¹⁴. Policy-measures have so far failed to adequately address this issue.

It's time to act – to ensure global food security today and a livable future

We have presented three levers to address the current food crisis while keeping long-term sustainability goals in mind. In addition to these overarching strategies, further short-term actions by European governments should be taken to ensure that vulnerable people in poor, food-importing countries do not fall into food insecurity. These actions include providing funds to the World Food Programme to purchase grains and keeping trade open, including food trade to and from Russia. Furthermore, social-security systems and food banks need to be strengthened across the EU to avoid detrimental effects of rising food prices for poor households. Effective long-term action however needs to tackle the inequalities of the current food system, in which hunger, waste, and resource-intensive consumption patterns coexist.

Russia's invasion of Ukraine and the ongoing war have sent shock waves through the food system. How the current crisis is handled politically has far-reaching implications for each one of us. The recently published IPCC report states that there is only a short window of opportunity left for effective action in the face of accelerating climate change and other environmental crises¹⁵. Focusing on short-term solutions now without considering the longer-term consequences or integrating the wider picture exacerbates future risks including the threat of surpassing critical tipping points of our planet's natural systems. Investing in a transition towards healthy and sustainable food systems now is essential to increase our resilience against future crises and ensure a safe and livable planet for generations to come.

Authors: Lisa M. Pörtner^{1,2}, Nathalie Lambrecht^{1,2}, Marco Springmann³, Benjamin Leon Bodirsky^{2,4}, Franziska Gaupp^{2,5}, Florian Freund⁶, Hermann Lotze-Campen^{2,7}, Sabine Gabrysch^{1,2}

1. Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, corporate member of Freie Universität Berlin and Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Institute of Public Health, Charitéplatz 1, 10117 Berlin, Germany
2. Research Department Climate Resilience, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Member of the Leibniz Association, P.O. Box 60 12 03, 14412 Potsdam, Germany
3. Oxford Martin Programme on the Future of Food and Nuffield Department of Population Health, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK.
4. World Vegetable Center, Tainan, Taiwan
5. EAT, Oslo, Norway
6. Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute - Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries, Institute of Market Analysis, Bundesallee 63, 38116 Braunschweig
7. Department of Agricultural Economics, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, 10099 Berlin, Germany

¹³Shafiee-Jood et al. (2016). Reducing food loss and waste to enhance food security and environmental sustainability. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 50(16), 8432–8443. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b01993>

¹⁴Willett et al. (2019)

¹⁵IPCC, 2022.

Co-Signatories:

1. Prof. Dr. Josef Settele, Co-Chair of IPBES Global Assessment; Head of Dept. of Conservation Biology and Social-Ecological Systems, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Halle, Germany
2. Prof. Dr. Hans-O. Pörtner, Head of Integrative Ecophysiology, Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Bremerhaven, Germany. Co-Chair of first joint IPBES-IPCC workshop and report on Biodiversity and Climate Change
3. Prof. Johan Rockström, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
4. Professor Jessica Fanzo, nutritionist, Johns Hopkins University, USA
5. Dr Tara Garnett, University of Oxford / Oxford Martin School, United Kingdom
6. Prof. Dr. Harald Grethe, Thae-Institute, Humboldt-University of Berlin
7. Prof Olivier De Schutter, UCLouvain, Belgium, former UN Special Rapporteur on the right to food, co-chair, IPES-Food, Belgium
8. Dr Rachel Nugent, RTI International and University of Washington, Seattle, WA, USA
9. Prof. Dr. Friedhelm Taube, University of Kiel, Germany
10. Professor Johannes Vogel, Ph.D., Museum für Naturkunde - Leibniz-Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science (Berlin), Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
11. Dr Sébastien Treyer, Executive Director, IDDRI, Sciences Po, Paris, France
12. Prof. Dr Eva Rehfuss, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (LMU Munich) and Pettenkofer School of Public Health, Germany
13. Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Cramer, CNRS-IMBE, Académie d'Agriculture de France, Aix-en-Provence, France
14. Prof. Dr. Almut Arneht, KIT, Atmospheric Environmental Research, Garmisch-Partenkirchen, Germany
15. Dr. Irmgard Jordan, Alliance Bioversity and CIAT
16. Dr. Adrian Leip, Bioeconomy, Brussels, Belgium
17. Dr. Margareta Büning-Fesel, Director General, Federal Centre for Nutrition, Bonn, Germany
18. Prof. Emeritus Howard Frumkin, University of Washington, USA
19. Professor Rachel Bezner Kerr, Department of Global Development, Cornell University, Ithaca USA
20. Professor Jonathan Patz, Director, Global Health Institute of the University of Wisconsin-Madison
21. Prof. Dr. Dr. Martina Schäfer, Center for Technology and Society, Technische Universität Berlin, Berlin, Germany
22. Prof. Dr. Jörg Niewöhner, Human-Environment Systems, IRI THESys, HU Berlin, Germany
23. Emeritus Prof. Barbara Harriss-White, Wolfson College, Oxford University, UK
24. Prof. Sir Andy Haines, Professor of Environmental Change and Public Health, Centre for Climate Change and Planetary Health, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, UK
25. Prof Soora Naresh Kumar, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, India
26. Dr Jody Harris, Institute of Development Studies, UK
27. Dr. Srinivasan Ramasamy, World Vegetable Center, Shanhua, Tainan, Taiwan

28. Dr. Wafaie Fawzi, Richard Saltonstall Professor of Population Sciences, and Professor of Nutrition, Epidemiology and Global Health, Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health, Boston, MA, USA
29. Dr Ana Pereira, Institute of Nutrition and Food Technology, University of Chile, Santiago, Chile
30. Prof. Dr. Ralf Seppelt, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Martin-Luther University Halle-Wittenberg.
31. Dr. Fabrice DeClerck, EAT and Alliance of Bioversity and CIAT of the CGIAR. Montpellier, France
32. Prof. Dr. Patrick Webb, Friedman School of Nutrition Science and Policy, Tufts University, Boston, USA
33. Prof. Dr. Ir. Peter H. Verburg, VU University Amsterdam & Swiss Federal Research Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL.
34. Dr. Samuel Myers, Department of Environmental Health, Harvard School of Public Health
35. Prof. Dr. Wilfried Winiwarter, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Laxenburg, Austria
36. Prof. Dr. Mark Lawrence, Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies, Potsdam, Germany
37. Prof. Michael Obersteiner, Environmental Change Institute, University of Oxford, UK
38. Prof. Dr. Keith P. West, Jr., Department of International Health, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, Baltimore, Maryland, USA
39. Dr. Birgit Müller, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Leipzig, Germany
40. Prof. Philippe Ciais, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, Gif sur Yvette France
41. Professor Peter Scarborough, University of Oxford, UK
42. Dr. Esther Boere, Biodiversity and Natural Resources Program, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austria
43. Prof. Dr. Anette Buyken, Institute for Nutrition, Consumption and Health, Paderborn University, Germany
44. Prof. Dr. Christoph Schneider, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
45. Dr. Prajal Pradhan, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
46. Prof. Dr. Peter H. Feindt, Agricultural and Food Policy Group, Thuer Institute for Agricultural and Horticultural Sciences, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
47. Dr. Peter von Philipsborn, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (LMU Munich) and Pettenkofer School of Public Health, Germany
48. Dr. Susanne Hanger-Kopp, Climate Policy Lab, ETH Zürich
49. Jun.-Prof. Dr. Laura M. König, University of Bayreuth, Germany
50. Dr Pierre-Marie Aubert, Institute for Sustainable Development and International Relations (Iddri)
51. Prof. Mark Pelling, King's College London, UK
52. PD Dr. Christian Schulz, AG Klimawandel, Klinik für Anästhesiologie und Intensivmedizin, Technische Universität München
53. Dr. Barbara Hentzsch, Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research
54. Dr. Steven Lord, Environmental Change Institute, University of Oxford, UK
55. Prof. Lindsay C Stringer, University of York, UK

56. Dr. Tim G Williams, Institute for Environmental Studies, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
57. Dr. Anne Elise Stratton, Institute Prof Environmental Studies, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the Netherlands
58. Dr. Lisa Schipper, University of Oxford and University of Vienna
59. Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Kießling, Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg
60. Dr. Dariush Mozaffarian, Friedman School of Nutrition Science & Policy, Tufts University, USA
61. Camille Venier-Cambron, PhD Candidate, IVM VU Amsterdam
62. Prof. Dr. Anita Engels, Universität Hamburg, Germany
63. Dr. Jennifer Cole, Royal Holloway University of London, UK.
64. Prof. Dr. Rita Adrian, Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, Berlin, Germany
65. Dr. Lukas Fesenfeld, ETH Zürich and Oeschger Centre for Climate Change Research at University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland
66. PD Dr. Christian S. Keßler, M.A., M.Sc.; Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany
67. Dr. Martin Herrmann KLUG Deutsche Allianz Klimawandel und Gesundheit, Munich Germany
68. Gianluca Brunori, PAGE group University of Pisa, Italy
69. Prof (Adj.) Dr Ian Darnton-Hill AO, University of Sydney, Australia
70. Prof. Johannes Mann, University of Erlangen, Germany
71. Dr. Bernhard Goodwin, Munich Science Communication Lab, LMU Munich, Germany
72. Prof. Jeffrey B. Blumberg, Tufts University, Boston, MA USA
73. Prof. Dr. Christof Mauch, Rachel Carson Center for Environment and Society, LMU Munich, Germany
74. Dr. Martin Jung, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Laxenburg, Austria
75. Dr. Michael Beckmann, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Leipzig Germany
76. Dr. Florian Zabel, Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich, Germany.
77. Maïke Voss, German Alliance on Climate Change and Health (KLUG), Berlin, Germany
78. Prof. Camille Parmesan, Make Our Planet Great Again Laureate, Theoretical and Experimental Ecology Station (SETE), CNRS, France
79. Jan-Frederic Kuhlmann, PhD Candidate, Ludwigs-Maximilians-Universität (LMU) München
80. Prof. Dr. Patrick Hostert, Geography Department, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
81. Prof. Dr. Dagmar Mithöfer, Thae-Institute of Agricultural and Horticultural Sciences, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
82. Prof Daniela Schmidt, Cabot Institute & University of Bristol, UK
83. Matthias Siebeck, Center for International Health, LMU Hospital, Munich, Germany
84. Prof. Dr. Jan Börner, Institute for Food and Resource Economics & Center for Development Research, University of Bonn, Germany
85. Dr. med. Eva-Maria Schwienhorst-Stich, MSciH, Planetary Health Unit, University of Würzburg Medical School and Department of General Practice, University Hospital Würzburg, Germany
86. Dr. Klaus Jacob, Freie Universität Berlin
87. Professor Mike Rayner, University of Oxford, UK

88. Dr. Gordon Fitch, University of Massachusetts Amherst, USA
89. Dr. Elias Charles Nyanza, Catholic University of Health and Allied Sciences, MWANZA, Tanzania.
90. Professor Holly K. Gibbs, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA
91. Professor Owen T. Lewis, University of Oxford, UK
92. Lesli Hoey, Sustainable Food Systems Initiative, University of Michigan, USA
93. Dr. Claudia Hunecke, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
94. Prof. Dr. Henny Annette Grewe, Public Health Institute Fulda
95. Dr. Valentin Fiala, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
96. Dr. med. Hannah Richter, Global Advisory Council on Global Change, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
97. Dr. Tatiana Schreiber, Environmental Studies, Keene State College, USA
98. Professor Emeritus Bruno Borsari, Department of Biology, Winona State University, Winona, MN 55987, USA
99. Dr. med. Kristin Hünninghaus, University Hospital Essen, Germany
100. Dr. Erin Coughlan de Perez, Feinstein International Center, Friedman School of Nutrition Science & Policy, Tufts University, USA
101. Prof. Martin Fischer, Institute of Medical Education, University Hospital, LMU Munich, Munich, Germany
102. PD Dr. Guenter Froeschl, Center for International Health, LMU Munich
103. Prof Lilia Ahrné, Department of University of Copenhagen, Denmark
104. Dr. Simone K. Frey, Nutrition Hub, Berlin, Germany
105. Amanda Harding, Convene
106. Dr. Melanie Schneider, Institute of Health Sciences, University of Education Schwäbisch Gmünd, Germany
107. Professor Molly Anderson, Middlebury College, Middlebury, VT, USA
108. Prof. Tobias Kuemmerle, Geography Department, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
109. Stefano Bisoffi, Independent expert, Italy
110. Katharina Wabnitz MD, MSc, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität Munich, Germany & German Alliance on Climate Change and Health (KLUG)
111. Philippe Huneman, Research Director, IHPST, CNRS, Paris
112. Prof. Dr. Dea Niebuhr, Fulda University of Applied Sciences, Fulda Public Health Centre, Germany
113. Dr. Alexandra Thorn, Gerald J. and Dorothy R. Friedman School of Nutrition Science and Policy, Tufts University, Boston USA
114. Niklas Oppenrieder MD, Physicians Association for Nutrition (PAN), Munich, Germany
115. Dr Alexander Popp, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
116. Dr. Christian Abshagen, MBA, University Hospital Basel and School of Life Sciences University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland
117. Prof. Dr. Kerstin Cuhls, Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, Karlsruhe, and University of Heidelberg.
118. Prof. Dr. Louise Willemen, Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation, University of Twente, Netherlands

119. Prof. Dr. Andy Nelson, Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation, University of Twente, Netherlands
120. Jun-Prof. Lisa Biber-Freudenberger, Center for Development Research, Bonn University, Germany
121. Prof. Dr. med. Clarissa Prazeres da Costa, Center for Global Health, School of Medicine, Technical University Munich (TUM), Germany
122. Dr Pauline Scheelbeek, Centre on Climate Change & Planetary Health, London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
123. Dr. Florian Humpenöder, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
124. Dr Alberte Bondeau, CNRS, Mediterranean Institute for marine and terrestrial Biodiversity and Ecology, Aix-Marseille University, Aix-en-Provence, France
125. Dr. Christoph Müller, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
126. Prof. a. D. Wolfgang Bokelmann, Thae Institute of Agricultural and Horticultural Science, Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany
127. Dr. Anne Lotte Potzel, Physicians Association for Nutrition (PAN), Munich, Germany
128. Dr. Alexandra Schneider, Institute for Epidemiology, Helmholtz Zentrum München (HMGU), Neuherberg, Germany
129. Prof. Dr. Heike Lotze, Department of Biology, Dalhousie University, Halifax, Canada
130. Dr. Marion Desquilbet, Toulouse School of Economics, INRAE, Toulouse, France
131. Prof. Dr. Markus Reichsten, Max-Planck-Institute for Biogeochemistry, Jena
132. Prof. Dr. Philippe Baret, Université de Louvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium
133. Dr Eve Fouilleux, CNRS-LISIS, CIRAD-MoISA (Montpellier Interdisciplinary Center for Sustainable Agri-Food Systems), Montpellier University, France
134. Prof. Ivette Perfecto, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI, USA
135. Prof. Dr. Eike Luedeling, Institute of Crop Science and Resource Conservation, University of Bonn, Germany
136. Dr. Jennifer N. Nielsen, Senior Nutrition Advisor, Helen Keller International, New York, NY, USA
137. Prof. Dr. Dr. Kurt Christian Kersebaum, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research, Müncheberg, Germany
138. Prof. Dr. Heidi Webber, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research, Müncheberg, Germany
139. Prof. Dr. Ralf Ludwig, Department of Geography, LMU Munich, Germany
140. Dr. Toby D. Pilditch, University of Oxford and University College London
141. Dr. Tom van Mourik, Global Food Systems Advisor, Helen Keller International, Haarlem, The Netherlands
142. Dr Laurence Gaume, CNRS-INEE (National Institute for Ecology and Environment), AMAP, Montpellier University, France.
143. Dr Etienne-Pascal Journet, CNRS and INRAE (National research institute for agriculture and environment), AGIR, Toulouse University, France
144. Dr Jeanne Pahun, Chaire santé de Sciences Po Paris, Paris, France
145. Dr Laurans Marilyne-CIRAD (French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development), AMAP, Montpellier University, France
146. Dr. Pierre Martre, LEPSE, Université Montpellier, INRAE, Institut Agro Montpellier, Montpellier, France

147. Prof. Dr. Anna Cord, Chair of Computational Landscape Ecology, TU Dresden, Germany
148. Nicolas Treich, Toulouse School of Economics, INRAE, Toulouse, France
149. Oleksandr Mialyk, PhD candidate, Multidisciplinary Water Management group, University of Twente, the Netherlands
150. François Warlop, Research Group in Organic Farming/Sciences Citoyennes, Avignon, France
151. Dr Peter Alexander, School of Geosciences, University of Edinburgh, UK
152. Dr Jean-Baptiste Floc'h, Centre pour la biodiversité, Institut de Recherche en Biologie Végétale, Montréal. Canada
153. Andrew Farlow, Nuffield Department of Medicine and Oxford Martin School, University of Oxford
154. Dany Neveu, Docteur en pharmacie, Université de Poitiers, France
155. Dr. Thomas Wassmer, Biology Department, Siena Heights University, Adrian, Michigan, USA
156. Théo Guillerminet, MSc in Ecology and evolutionary biology, University of Montpellier, France
157. Dr. Lisa Rausch, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA
158. Dr. Swetha Manohar, Johns Hopkins University, USA
159. Dr Naomi Saville, University College London, UK
160. Dr. Bruce G. Ferguson, Dept. of Agriculture, Society, and the Environment, El Colegio de la Frontera Sur, San Cristóbal de Las Casas, Mexico
161. Dr. Debora Ley, Economic Affairs Officer, Energy and Natural Resources, Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC)
162. Dr. Kathryn De Master, Department of Environmental Science, Policy, and Management, University of California, Berkeley
163. Dr. Daniel Müller, Department of Structural Change, Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO), Halle (Saale), Germany
164. Dr. Jonas Jägermeyr, Columbia University Climate School and NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies, New York, USA
165. Professor Andrew K L Robinson, Deputy Dean, North West University, Public Health Physician.
166. Stefanie Bühn, German Alliance on Climate Change and Health (KLUG), Berlin, Germany
167. Prof. Dr. Elmar Schulte-Geldermann, Department of Life Science, Bingen, University of Applied Sciences, Bingen am Rhein, Germany
168. Prof. Dr. Reimund P. Rötter, Department of Crop Sciences, University of Göttingen, Göttingen, Germany
169. Dr. Laura Kehoe, University of Oxford, UK; The Nature Conservancy, UK
170. Dr. Katja Schiffers, Institute of Crop Science and Resource Conservation, University of Bonn, Germany
171. Prof. Dr. Richard Lucius, FoodBerlin, Berlin, Germany.
172. Dr. David Leclère, Biodiversity and Natural Resources Program, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austria
173. Bina Agarwal, Professor of Development Economics and Environment, The University of Manchester, UK
174. Dr. Romain Espinosa, CIRED, CNRS, Paris, France

175. Dr. Kim Gruetzmacher, Museum für Naturkunde, Leibniz-Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Research
176. Prof. Nanette Ströbele-Benschop, University of Hohenheim, Germany
177. Dr. Annie Chateau, Bioinformatics, University of Montpellier, France
178. Dr. Nathalie de Noblet-Ducoudré, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, CEA; Académie d'Agriculture de France; Paris, France
179. Dr. Christian Folberth, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Laxenburg, Austria
180. Dr. Alexandre Courtiol, Leibniz Institute for Zoo & Wildlife Research, Berlin, Germany
181. Prof. Dr. Martin Smollich, Institute of Nutritional Medicine, University Medical Center Schleswig-Holstein, Lübeck, Germany
182. Dr. Clelia Sirami, French National Research Institute on Agriculture, Food and Environment, Toulouse, France.
183. Prof. Dr. Jessica Aschemann-Witzel, MAPP Center for Research in Food Marketing and Consumer Behaviour, Department of Management, Aarhus University
184. Dr. Marten Graubner, Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO), Halle (Saale), Germany
185. Dr. Guillaume Martin, French National Research Institute on Agriculture, Food and Environment, Toulouse, France.
186. Gabi Waldhof, Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO), Halle (Saale), Germany
187. Prof. Dr. a.D. Alois Heißenhuber, Agricultural Economics and Farm Management, Technische Universität München-Weihenstephan
188. Dr. Florence Volaire, French National Institute for Agronomic Research and environment (INRAE), Montpellier, France
189. Dr. Raphaël Manlay, AgroParisTech, Montpellier, France
190. Prof. Dr. Bernhard Schauburger, University of Applied Sciences Weihenstephan-Triesdorf & Potsdam Institute for Climate Impacts Research (PIK)
191. Dr. Philippe Grandcolas, Director, Institut de Systématique, Evolution et Biodiversité, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, CNRS, Sorbonne Université, EPHE, UA, CP50, 57 rue Cuvier, 75005 Paris, France
192. Dr. Vivian Valencia, Assistant Professor, Farming Systems Ecology, Wageningen University and Research, The Netherlands
193. Dr. Silvia De Monte, IBENS, PSL Research University, Paris, France and Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology, Plön, Germany
194. Dr. Olivier Jaillon, CEA, Genoscope, Evry, France
195. Dr. Sabrina Schulz, Executive Director, Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN) Germany
196. Dr. Jeroen Candel, Associate Professor of Food and Agricultural Policy, Wageningen University, the Netherlands.
197. Dr. Chantal Le Mouél, French National Research Institute on Agriculture, Food and Environment, Rennes, France.
198. Dr. Tomáš Václavík, Associate Professor, Department of Ecology and Environmental Sciences, Palacký university Olomouc, Czech Republic
199. Dr. Josette Garnier, Research Director CNRS, Metis 7619, Sorbonne Université, Paris, France

200. Dr. Christoph Schmitz, Founder and Managing Director of Acker e.V., Bessemerstr. 2-14, 12103 Berlin
201. Dr. Ulrich Kreidenweis, Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB), Potsdam, Germany
202. Dr. Patricia Genet, Professor assistant, Institute of ecology and environmental sciences of Paris, Université Paris Cité, France
203. Dr. Dilini Abeygunawardane, Research Associate, Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO), Halle (Saale), Germany
204. Dr. Friedrich J. Bohn, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Leipzig, Germany
205. Dr. Christian Mougin, Research Director, INRAE, ECOSYS, Versailles, France
206. Dr. Sarah Jones, Scientist, Alliance of Bioversity International and International Center for Tropical Agroforestry, Montpellier, France
207. Dr. Kati Krähnert, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK)
208. Dr. François Chiron, Université Paris Saclay, Ecology Systematics Evolution, Orsay, France
209. Dr. Raphaël Antoine, Research Scientist, Centre for Studies on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning (Cerema), Endsum research team, Rouen, France
210. Dr. Fabienne Barataud, Research Engineer, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Nancy, France
211. Dr. Hélène I Joly, CIRAD, Crop evolution scientist, research unit AGAP (Plant adaptation and plant breeding), Dynamics of Diversity, Societies and Environment team. Montpellier, France
212. Dr. Sarah Scholze, Center for International Health, LMU Munich
213. Dr. Denis Lairon, Emeritus research director at INSERM, Human nutrition team-Sustainable food systems at Cardio-vascular and nutrition research center INSERM-INRAE-AMU, Faculty of Medicine, Aix-Marseille University, France
214. Dr. Jean-Michel Olivier, research engineer CNRS, UMR CNRS 5023-LEHNA, University of Lyon France
215. Dr. Manon Fallet, Postdoctoral researcher at MTM Research Center, Örebro University, Sweden
216. Prof. Michael Bonsall, University of Oxford, United Kingdom.
217. Jérôme Belliard, Research Engineer, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), HYCAR RU, Antony, France
218. Dr. Gabrielle Bouleau, Research Scientist, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Champs-sur-Marne, France
219. Catherine Donnars, Research Engineer, French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment, Paris, France.
220. Dr. Emmanuelle Kesse-Guyot, Senior Researcher, INRAE, France.
221. Dr. Timothée Cook, Science Officer at BlueSeeds, Darwin Ecosystem, Bordeaux, France
222. Dr. Thierry Desjardins, IRD, Paris, France
223. Dr. Ing. Martin Seidl, Senior researcher, LEESU ENPC, Champs-Marne, France
224. Dr. Anja Hansen, Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB), Potsdam, Germany.

225. Dr. Alberto Sanz-Cobena, Associate Professor at the Research Center for the Management of Agricultural and Environmental Risks (CEIGRAM) of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM, Spain).
226. Jun.Prof. Dr. Antje Risius, Professur Ernährung Gesundheit und Nachhaltigkeit, Pädagogische Hochschule Schwäbisch Gmünd/Universität Göttingen (Germany)
227. Dr. Christine Hatté, researcher at the Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement (Gif-sur-Yvette, France) and associate professor at the Silesian University of Technology (Gliwice, Poland)
228. Dr Thomas Pugh, Senior Lecturer, Lund University, Sweden.
229. Dr Jan Ellenberger, Researcher at the Institute of Crop Science and Resource Conservation, University of Bonn, Germany.
230. Carmen Klinger, PhD Candidate, Ludwigs-Maximilians-Universität (LMU) München
231. Pierre-Alain Jayet, DR INRAE (National research institute for agriculture, food and environment)
232. Pr. Jean-Marie Mouchel, Sorbonne Université, Paris.
233. Thomas Puech, Research Ingeneer, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Mirecourt, France
234. Mr. Olav Kjørven, Senior Director of Strategy, EAT Foundation, Oslo, Norway
235. Dr. Gesa Maschkowski, Federal Centre for Nutrition, Bonn, Germany.
236. Masihullah Hasanyar, Doctorant, Mines ParisTech, Fontainebleau, France
237. Dr. Kai Kornhuber, Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory, Columbia University, NYC
238. Dr. Agnès Rivièrè, researcher at Mines ParisTech, PSL University, Paris, France
239. Dr. Michel Meybeck, Senior scientist, CNRS, Sorbonne Université, Paris, France
240. Ivanka Puigdueta Bartolomé, MSc in Environmental Sciences, Research Centre for the Management of Agricultural and Environmental Risks (CEIGRAM), Spain
241. Dr. Carmen Bessa Gomes, Associate Professor, AgroParisTech, Paris, France
242. Dr. Niels Debonne, postdoctoral researcher, Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL and VU Amsterdam, Switzerland/the Netherlands
243. Dr. Christian Levers, Assistant Professor, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, The Netherlands
244. Marie Aureille, PhD Candidate, Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales, Paris, France
245. Dr Thierry Desjardins, IRD, Paris, France
246. Dr. Rasmus Einarsson, Postdoctoral researcher at the Research Center for the Management of Agricultural and Environmental Risks (CEIGRAM), Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Spain
247. Prof Pete Smith FRS, FRSE, Professor of Soils & Global Change, University of Aberdeen, Scotland, UK
248. Dr. François Bonhomme, Directeur de recherches émérite, Université de Montpellier, France
249. Dr. Hervé Philippe, Directeur de recherche, Station d'Écologie Théorique et Expérimentale, UAR CNRS 2029
250. Dr. Yasmina Boussafir, Ingénieure, Université Gustave Eiffel, Département Géotechnique Environnement Risques naturels Sciences de la terre, Campus Marne-la-Vallée, France
251. Bram Droppers, PhD, Wageningen University, Wageningen, The Netherlands
252. Dr. Pietro Barbieri, Associate Professor, Bordeaux Sciences Agro, Bordeaux, France

253. Dr. Michael Hagenlocher, Associate Academic Officer, United Nations University, Institute for Environment and Human Security (UNU-EHS), Bonn, Germany
254. Dr. Amanda Wendt, Climate Change and Health Working Group, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
255. Dr. Yue Dou, Assistant professor, Natural Resource Department, Faculty of Geoinformation Science and Earth Observation, University of Twente, the Netherlands
256. Dr. Julie Augustin, Postdoctoral researcher, French Agricultural Research Center for International Development (CIRAD)
257. Dr. Janine Pelikan, Deputy Director, Thünen Institute of Market Analysis.
258. Dr. Julia Baudry, researcher, INRAE, France
259. Bea Bardusch, researcher at Thünen Institute of Market Analysis.
260. Dr. Marco Heinrich, researcher at Thünen Institute of Market Analysis
261. Prof. Dr. Martin Banse, Director, Thünen Institute of Market Analysis
262. Dr. Felicitas Schneider, researcher at Thünen Institute of Market Analysis, Germany
263. Dr. Josef Efken, researcher at Thünen Institute of Market Analysis, Germany
264. Dr. Sebastian Brandis, Speaker of the Board, Stiftung Menschen für Menschen-Karlheinz Böhms Äthiopienhilfe
265. Dr. Anthony Fardet, Research Scientist, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Clermont-Ferrand/Theix, France
266. Dr Marko Kerac, Associate Professor, London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, UK
267. Dr. Meredith Jackson-deGraffenried, Global Technical Advisor, Helen Keller Intl, Malawi
268. Dr Clotilde Biard, Associate Professor, Sorbonne Université, Institute of Ecology and Environmental Sciences IEES-Paris, Paris, France
269. Dr Rémi Tournebize, Postdoc, Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciência, Oeiras, Portugal
270. Fabian Jacobs, Institute of Medical Education, University Hospital, LMU Munich, Munich, Germany
271. Dr. Ivica Faletar, Researcher at Thünen Institute of Market Analysis, Germany
272. Dr. Julio G. Fournier Gabela, researcher at Thünen Institute of Market Analysis, Germany
273. Dr. Pierre Dupraz, Research Director, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Rennes, France
274. Dr. and Prof. Emeritus Gerald C. Nelson, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign, United States
275. Dr. David Kilian, researcher at Thünen Institute of Market Analysis, Germany
276. Dr Laurent Penet, researcher, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Petit Bourg, Guadeloupe
277. Elizabeth Zehner, Director, Assessment and Research on Child Feeding Project, Helen Keller International (ARCH), Washington, D.C., USA
278. Dr Vincent Daubin, CNRS, Laboratoire de Biométrie et Biologie Evolutive, Université de Lyon, France
279. Dr. Felix Herzog, Agroscope, Zurich, Switzerland
280. Dr. Julien Tournebize, Senior Researcher, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), HYCAR UR, Antony, France.
281. Dr. Michael Krawinkel, Prof. em., Justus-Liebig-University, Giessen, Germany

282. Dr Patrick A. Jansen, Associate professor, Wildlife Ecology and Conservation group, Wageningen University, The Netherlands.
283. Dr Jean Humphrey, Professor, Human Nutrition. Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, Baltimore, MD, USA.
284. Prof Dr. Thomas Nesme, Univ Bordeaux and INRAE, Bordeaux, France
285. Dr. Sam S. Rabin, Rutgers University, USA
286. PD Dr. Philipp Grundmann, Leibniz-Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB) and Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany
287. Prof Ian Hamilton, UCL Energy Institute, University College London, UK
288. Dr. Daniela Weible, researcher, Thünen-Institute of Market Analysis
289. Prof. dr. Roos Vonk, Radboud University, Behavioral Sciences Institute, The Netherlands
290. Dr. Bruno Dorin, Researcher (economics), Cirad/Cired, Paris, France
291. Kenneth A. Meter, MPA, President of Crossroads Resource Center, USA
292. Henk Folmer. Professor of Spatial Economics, University of Groningen, The Netherlands, Professor of Spatial Statistics, Padjadjaran University, Bandung, Indonesia, Founder and first president of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economics
293. Joel Guiot, emeritus CNRS, CEREGE, Aix-Marseille University, Aix-en-Provence, France
294. Prof. dr. Pim Martens, Maastricht University, The Netherlands
295. Dr. Carsten Meyer, German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, Germany
296. Prof. dr. Jeltsje van der Meer-Kooistra, University of Groningen, The Netherlands
297. Dr. Žiga Malek, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the Netherlands
298. Dr. ir. Ignas M.A. Heitkönig, Wildlife Ecology and Conservation group, Wageningen University, The Netherlands.
299. Prof. Dr Theunis Piersma, Rudi Drent Chair in Global Flyway Ecology, GELIFES, University of Groningen & senior research scientist NIOZ Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research
300. Emeritus Professor Robert Gottlieb, Occidental College, Los Angeles
301. Dr. Jeanne Nel, Programme Lead: Biodiversity Environment, Wageningen University & Research, the Netherlands
302. Prof. dr Liesje Mommer; Plant Ecology and Nature Conservation; Leader of the Wageningen Biodiversity Initiative; Wageningen University & Research, the Netherlands
303. Dr. Sandrine Dury, Cirad, Montpellier, France.
304. Dr Ludovic Temple, Cirad, Montpellier, France.
305. Prof. Dr Stéphane André; Université de Lorraine, Nancy, France
306. Dr. Nicolas Ferry, Postdoctoral researcher, Bavarian Forest National Park Administration, Germany.
307. Dr. Fabien Esculier, Ecole des Ponts ParisTech, France
308. Dr. Tristan Berchoux, Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Montpellier, France
309. Dr. Arnaud Béchet, Research Institute of Tour du Valat, Arles, France
310. Dr. Philippe Jarne, Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et Evolutive, CNRS, France
311. Dr. Lysanne Snijders, Behavioural Ecology Group, Wageningen University & Research, the Netherlands

312. François Mitteau, Conseil orientation recherche et prospective, fédération des parcs naturels régionaux de France
313. Dr Noémie Gaudio, INRAE (National research institute for agriculture, food and environment), AGIR, Toulouse University, France
314. Prof. Frederic Landy, université Paris Nanterre, France
315. Dr. Ralf Kurvers, MPI for Human Development, Berlin, Germany
316. Dr. Jörn Sanders, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland
317. Dr Jean-Marc Meynard, Senior Researcher, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Grignon, France
318. Gilles Maréchal, chercheur associé, CNRS, Rennes, France
319. Dr Frédéric Magnin, CNRS - IMBE, Aix-en-Provence, France
320. Dr. Laura Michel, senior social scientist, Université de Montpellier, France
321. Borah Lim, University of California, Davis, USA
322. Dr Sophie Gerber, INRAE and Univ Bordeaux, France
323. Prof. Philippe Martin, AgroParisTech and National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Paris, France
324. Dr Nicolas Legay, INSA Centre Val de Loire, CITERES, Blois, France
325. Dr Raphael Leblois, INRAE Montpellier, France
326. Dr. Sébastien Barot, Senior Scientist, IRD, France
327. Dr Romain Garrouste, Researcher MNHN, France
328. Dr Marie-Hélène Jeuffroy, Senior Researcher, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France
329. Dr Albert Olioso, Senior Researcher, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France
330. Dr Xavier Poux, Researcher, AScA and IDDRI, France
331. Dr. Chloé Salembier, Researcher, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France
332. Prof Laurence Després, Université Grenoble Alpes, France
333. Prof. Carole Hermon, Toulouse University, France
334. Dr Isabelle Arpin, Senior Scientist, INRAE, France
335. Prof. Dominique Bourg, honoraire, Université de Lausanne, Suisse
336. Dr. Olivier Godinot, Institut Agro, Rennes, France
337. Prof. Nathalie Frascaria-Lacoste, AgroParisTech, Université Paris-Saclay, France
338. Dr. Mary Stockdale, Department of Community, Culture and Global Studies, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, University of British Columbia, Okanagan campus, BC, Canada
339. Dr. Gilles Nalbone, Emeritus research director at INSERM, Aix-Marseille-University.
340. Dr. Grégoire Freschet, Senior Scientist, CNRS, France
341. Dr Fabien Quétier, biodiversity and ecosystem restoration specialist, Rewilding Europe
342. Dr Floriane Clément, Researcher, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France
343. Dr Sylvaine Lemeilleur, researcher, CIRAD, France
344. Dr Marie Mourad, Food Waste Specialist, independent consultant, France / U.S.
345. Prof. Alex Barnard, Assistant Professor of Sociology, New York University, U.S.

346. François Colson DR honoraire Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE), Nantes, France
347. Dr. Jean-François Molino, Botanist and Ecologist, Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD), France
348. Prof. Dr. Marie-Antoinette Mélières, honoraire, LGGE, Université Grenoble Alpes, France
349. Dr. Didier Bazile, agroecologist and geographer, senior researcher at CIRAD, France
350. Mathilde Douillet, agronomist, economist, Fondation Daniel & Nina Carasso, France
351. Prof. Sylvie Ferrari, Ecological economist, Bordeaux School of Economics, University of Bordeaux, France
352. Dr. Yves Martin-Prevel, public health nutritionist, senior researcher at IRD, Montpellier, France
353. Prof. Claude Miaud, ecologist, senior scientist at EPHE, Montpellier, France
354. Dr. Isabelle Doussan, jurist, senior researcher at INRAE, France
355. Prof. Dr. Anke Weidenkaff, Materials and Resources, Technical University Darmstadt
356. Dr. Christine Lauzeral, PRAG, EDB, Université Toulouse III, Paul Sabatier, France.
357. Dr Mourad Hannachi, Researcher, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Grignon, France
358. Dr Carole Bedos, Researcher, INRAE, France
359. Dr Jean-Marc Pons, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France
360. Prof. Dr. Allison Marie Loconto, sociologist, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France
361. Dr Emmanuel Torquebiau, Agroforestry specialist, CIRAD (Emeritus), French Agricultural Research Center for International Development, Montpellier, France
362. Dr Antoine Leblois, Economist, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France.
363. Dr Benoit Ricci, Researcher in agroecology and agroforestry, INRAE, Montpellier, France
364. Dr Marc Deconchat, Landscape ecologist, INRAE, Toulouse, France
365. Dr Etienne Hainzelin, agronomist, CIRAD, Ottawa, Canada / Montpellier, France
366. Michel Duru, agronomist, INRAE, Toulouse, France
367. Dr Lionel Alletto, agronomist, INRAE, Toulouse, France
368. Prof. Alexandra Magro, evolutionary ecologist, University of Toulouse, France
369. Dr. Frédéric Rees, plant ecophysiologicalist, INRAE, Thiverval-Grignon, France
370. Prof. Jean-Pierre Sarthou, Agronomist-Agroecologist, University of Toulouse, France
371. Dr Simon Vonthron, Geographer, University of Liège, Belgium
372. Dr Simon Fellous, Research director in pest-management and ecology, INRAE, France
373. Sonja Schönberg, Research Dietitian, Bern University of Applied Sciences, Switzerland
374. Gaël Plumecocq, Researcher in economics, INRAE, Toulouse, France
375. Prof. Jane Lecomte, Ecology, Paris-Saclay University, Gif-sur-Yvette, France
376. Dr. Catherine Aubertin, Researcher in environmental economics, IRD-MNHN, France
377. Dr Claire Jouany, agronomist, INRAE, Toulouse, France
378. Emeritus Professor Doyle McKey, ecologist, University of Montpellier, France
379. Paola Clerino, agronomist, INRAE, Paris, France

380. Emeritus Professor Barbara Demeneix, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France
381. Dr. med. Antje Herbst, MPH, Klinikum Leverkusen, Klinik für Kinder und Jugendliche, Leverkusen, Germany
382. Pr Alexandra Jullien, ecophysiologicalist, AgroParisTech, Université Paris-Saclay, France
383. Professor Pierre Cornu, Late Modern History & History of Sciences, Lumière University Lyon 2 / Inrae, France
384. Prof. Dr. Claire Chenu, soil scientist INRAE, Grignon, France. Coordinator of the H2020 European Joint Programme SOIL.
385. Dr. Jacques Blondel, Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et Evolutive, CNRS, Montpellier, France
386. Professor Florence Pinton, environmental and rural sociology, Agroparistech, University Paris Saclay, France
387. Prof. Dr. Salma Loudiyi, geographer, VetAgro Sup, Clermont-Ferrand, France
388. Dr Marianne Cerf, Ergonomics, UMR SadApt, INRAE AgroParisTech, University Paris Saclay, France
389. Dr. Pierre-Benoit Joly, Economics and sociology, LISIS, INRAE, Paris, France
390. Dr. Sylvain Pellerin, agronomist, INRAE, France
391. Dr. Christine King, Researcher in earth science, natural hazards, BRGM, member of the French Academy of Agriculture
392. Dr. Francois Bousquet, social and ecological systems, UMR SENS, CIRAD
393. Dr Pierre Benoit, soil scientist, INRAE, Grignon, France
394. Dr Timothée Flutre, geneticist, INRAE, Université Paris-Saclay, France
395. Dr Alain Vidal, Consulting Professor, AgroParisTech, Montpellier, France
396. Dr Francesco Accatino, Researcher (socio-ecological modelling), UMR SadApt, INRAE AgroParisTech, University Paris Saclay, France
397. Ass. Pr. Christophe Déprés, economist, VetAgro Sup, Clermont-Ferrand, France
398. Dr Roseline Remans, Researcher on Biodiversity in Food systems, Glocolearning & Multi-functional Landscapes, Alliance of Bioversity and CIAT, CGIAR
399. Dr Mireille Navarrete, Senior Researcher, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Ecodéveloppement Unit, France
400. Prof. François Sarrazin, conservation ecology, CESCO, Sorbonne Université, Paris, France.
401. Dr. Amy Webb Girard, Associate Professor, Hubert Department of Global Health, Rollins School Of Public Health, Emory University Atlanta GA USA
402. Dr. med. Sarah Verweyen, M.A. Kulturwissenschaften & Komplementärmedizin, Germany
403. Dr. Abigail Fallot, UMR SENS, CIRAD France
404. Professor Ricardo Abramovay University of Sao Paulo (Environment Program)
405. Dr Benoît Lallau, Sciences Po Lille, France
406. Philippe Segers, Head of European HPC projects, GENCI, France
407. Dr. Jean-Philippe Choisis, agronomist, French National Research Institute on Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE), UMR Selmet, Montpellier, France.
408. Dr. David Grémillet, senior scientist at the French National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS). Centre d'Etudes Biologiques de Chizé (CEBC) / La Rochelle Université. Chaire d'Excellence Nouvelle Aquitaine. France.
409. Professor Dr Chevalier John R Porter, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

410. Dr. Yanne Goossens, researcher at Thünen Institute of Market Analysis, Germany
411. Luca Colombo, Secretary General, Italian Foundation for Research in Organic Agriculture (FIRAB), Italy
412. Dr Soizic Rochange, Toulouse University, France
413. Prof. Dr. Angela Häußler, Nutrition and Home Economics University of Education Heidelberg, Germany
414. Prof. Dr. Katja Schneider, Nutrition Ecology and Nutrition Education, University of Education Heidelberg, Germany
415. Dr Christine Aubry Agronomist, INRAE AgroParistech, France
416. Prof. Ranjan Kumar Ghosh, Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad, India
417. Dr. Cian Blaix, UMR GEOLAB, Université Clermont Auvergne, CNRS, France
418. Professor Sophie Devienne, Agroeconomist, Social and Economic Sciences, AgroParisTech, Paris
419. Dr. Marie Nevoux, INRAE, Dynamics and durability of ecosystems, France
420. Dr. Valentin Bellassen, Agricultural and food economics, INRAE, France
421. Dr Anne Teyssède, ecologist, Institut de la Transition Environnementale, Paris, France
422. Dr. Johanna Schott, researcher, Thünen-Institute of Market Analysis
423. Dr Rosemary Green, Associate Professor in Sustainability, Nutrition and Health, Centre on Climate Change and Planetary Health, London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, UK
424. Dr. Julian Helfenstein, postdoctoral researcher, Agroscope, Zürich, Switzerland
425. Dr. Caroline Brand, Lecturer, ISARA-LER, Lyon, France
426. Dr. Philippe Burger, agronomist, INRAE, Montpellier, France
427. Dr. Raphaël Paut, agronomist, INRAE, France
428. Dr. Benoît Geslin, Ecologist, Associate Professor, IMBE, Aix-Marseille Université, Avignon Université, CNRS, IRD, Marseille, France
429. Dr. Marie-Claude Marsolier, geneticist, CEA/MNHN, Paris, France
430. Dr. Marine Legrand, anthropologist, LEESU, Ecole des Ponts Paristech, Marne-la-Vallée, France
431. Dr. Christine Léger-Bosch, economist, INRAE, Clermont-Ferrand, France
432. Prof. Christian A. Kull, geographer, University of Lausanne, Switzerland
433. Dr. Antoine Gardarin, agronomist and ecologist, AgroParisTech, INRAE, France
434. Dr. Benjamin Loubet, Environmental scientist, INRAE, France
435. Dr. Nicole de Paula, Founder of the Women Leaders for Planetary Health and Affiliate Scholar at the Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies, Potsdam, Germany
436. Dr. Daniela Küllenberg de Gaudry. Independent expert, Freiburg, Germany
437. Pr Marianne Le Bail, agronomist, Agroparistech INRAE, Paris, France
438. Dr. Katja Kehlenbeck, Climate Change and Health Working Group, Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany
439. Dr. Barbara Kaiser, Federal Centre for Nutrition, Bonn, Germany
440. Dr. Gregor Hagedorn, Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, Germany
441. Dr. François Papy, Académie d'agriculture de France, France
442. Audrey Béthinger, Research engineer, INRAE, France
443. Christian Feist, CEO, GESOCA GmbH
444. Françoise Lescourret, agroecologist, INRAE, Avignon, France
445. Dr. Marianne Lefebvre, agricultural economist, Angers, France

446. Dr. Hayo van der Werf, agroecologist, INRAE, France
447. Dr. Luc Bodiguel, Agricultural and Food Lawer, CNRS, France
448. Dr. Alexander Beck, Managing board member, AöL e.V., Germany
449. Dr. Benoît Fontaine, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, France
450. Dr. Pauline Marty, UR InSyTE, Université de Technologie de Troyes, France
451. Dr. Loïc Viguier, Research engineer, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France
452. Prof. Stefan Rahmstorf, climatologist, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Germany
453. Dr. Ir. A.R. Hof, Wildlife Ecology and Conservation group, Wageningen University, The Netherlands
454. Prof. em. Michael B. Krawinkel, MD, Institute of Nutritional Sciences, Justus-Liebig-University, Giessen, Germany
455. Dr. Nicolas Gross, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France
456. Julie Borg, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Avignon, France
457. Dr. Francine Van den Brandeler, Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (Eawag), Dübendorf, Switzerland
458. Prof. Dr. Jelle Bijma, Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Helmholtz Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung (AWI), Bremerhaven, Germany
459. Dr Frédéric Madre, Directeur associé de Topager, chercheur associé au CESCO (MNHN-CNRS-Sorbonne Université), Paris, France
460. Prof. Dr. Claus-Heinrich Daub, University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland, Windisch, and University of Basel, Switzerland
461. Prof. Emeritus Mark L. Wilson, University of Michigan, USA
462. Prof. Dr. Werner Aeschbach, Institute of Environmental Physics, Heidelberg University, Germany
463. Dr. Martin Drenthen, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands
464. Dr. François Massol, ecologist, senior scientist at the French National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS), Lille, France
465. Dr. Delphine Leenhardt, agronomist, INRAE, Montpellier, France
466. Dr. Lucille Steinmetz, Agence BIO, Montreuil, France
467. Michel Duru, agronomist, INRAE, Toulouse, France
468. Prof. Line Gordon, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
469. Dr. Françoise Burel, Emeritus ecologist, CNRS, Rennes, France
470. Dr. András Báldi, Centre for Ecological Research, Vácrátót, Hungary
471. Dr. Olivier Barreteau, water scientist, INRAE, Montpellier, France
472. Dr. Ingo Fetzer, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
473. Prof. Dr. Michael Weiß, Steinbeis Innovation Center: Organismal Mycology and Microbiology, Tübingen, Germany
474. Dr. Nathalie Becker, Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France
475. Sophie Frei, Nutritionist, independent expert, Bern, Switzerland
476. Dr. Max Troell, Beijer Institute, The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, 10405 Stockholm, Sweden
477. Dr Jean-Marc Bonmatin, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Centre de Biophysique Moléculaire, 45071 Orléans, France
478. Dr Laurence Huc, INRAE, Toxalim, Toulouse, France

479. Dr Laure Hossard, Researcher in Agronomy, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Innovation, Montpellier, France
480. Polina Voylokova, French National Institute for Agronomic Research and environment (INRAE) Thiverval-Grignon, France
481. Dr Olivier Duchene, Agronomist, ISARA, Lyon, France
482. Dr Léa Tison, Ecotoxicologist, INRAE, Bordeaux, France
483. Dr Delphine Marie-Vivien, Researcher in Food Law, UMR Innovation, CIRAD (French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development), Montpellier, France
484. Nicolas Bricas, researcher in socio-economics of food systems, UMR MoISA, Cirad (French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development) and Director of the Unesco Chair in World Food Systems, Montpellier University, France
485. Martine Antona, social scientist, Commons and Biodiversity, UMR SENS, CIRAD, Montpellier, France
486. Dr Philippe Gaubert, researcher in biodiversity conservation, UMR EDB, Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD), Toulouse, France
487. Dr. Cornelia Huth, MSc, Epidemiologist and Medical Science Manager, medi, Bayreuth, Germany
488. Olivier Therond, HDR, landscape agronomist, UMR LAE, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Colmar France
489. Carolina Orellana-Torrejon, PhD student, agronomist, AgroParisTech, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Grignon, France
490. Dr Nelly Moulin, researcher at Agriculture Institute (Agrocampus), Rennes, France
491. Dr Nathalie Hostiou, researcher, UMR Territoires, French National Research Institute For Agriculture, Food and Environment
492. Dr Christian Bockstaller, systemic agronomist, UMR LAE, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Colmar France
493. Dr Audrey Alignier, landscape ecologist, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Rennes, France
494. Anne Carolin Schäfer, PhD-Candidate, Scientific department, German Nutrition Society (DGE), Bonn, Germany
495. Dr. My Sellberg, researcher at Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
496. Dr. Koladé Akakpo, research fellow, CIRAD, Montpellier, France
497. Dr. Lan Wang-Erlandsson, researcher at Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
498. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Andreas Pfennig, Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Liège, Belgium
499. Dr. Carsten Neßhöver, geoecologist, Coordinator International Academy Transformation for Environment and Sustainability, German Environment Agency (UBA), Germany
500. Dr Alain Baranger, geneticist, French National Institute for Agronomic Research and Environment, Rennes, France
501. Dr. Susanne Rolinski, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
502. Dr. Maud Charles, French National Institute for Agronomic Research and environment (INRAE), Rennes, France

503. Dr. Giles B. Sioen, Co-lead for Research and Innovation, Future Earth Global Secretariat, Japan
504. Prof. Dr. Hans-Peter Grosart, microbial ecologist, Leibniz Institute for Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB), Berlin, Germany
505. Dr. Eduardo Aguilera, Research Center for the Management of Agricultural and Environmental Risks (CEIGRAM), Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM, Spain)
506. Dr. Judith Bopp, VISTRA, University of Vechta, Germany
507. Prof. Dr. Robert Finger, ETH Zürich, Switzerland
508. Prof. Dr. Christoph Gornott, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK) & University of Kassel, Potsdam & Kassel, Germany
509. Dr. Bettina Wenzel, Julius Kühn Institut - Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants, Kleinmachnow, Germany
510. Dra. Gloria I. Guzmán, Agro-ecosystems History Laboratory, Pablo de Olavide University (UPO, Sevilla, Spain)
511. Dr. Tonjes Veenstra, Leibniz-Centre General Linguistics (ZAS), Berlin, Germany
512. Prof. Dr. Nina Buchmann, ETH Zürich, Switzerland
513. Prof. Dr. Bettina Matzdorf, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Research (ZALF) Müncheberg, Germany
514. Dr. Louisa Prause, Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany
515. Prof. Sebastian Villasante, Economist, CRETUS-Department of Applied Economics, University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain
516. Dr. Toni Klemm, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Research (ZALF) Müncheberg, Germany
517. Dr. Joan Moranta, Centre Oceanogràfic de Balears, CN Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO, CSIC), Mallorca, Spain
518. Dr. Johannes Fehrle, Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany
519. Dr. Karine Princé, Research Associate CESCO - Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France
520. Dr. Frank Liebisch, Head of water protection and substance flows research group at Agroscope, Zürich Switzerland
521. Dr. Renzo Guinto, Chief Planetary Health Scientist, Sunway Centre for Planetary Health, Sunway University, Malaysia and Director, Planetary and Global Health Program, St. Luke's Medical Center College of Medicine, Philippines
522. Prof. Dr. Christine Brombach, Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Wädenswil, Switzerland
523. Dr. Asya Dimitrova, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Potsdam, Germany
524. PD Dr. Valentin H. Klaus, ETH Zürich, Zürich, Switzerland
525. Prof. Nadav Davidovitch, Director, School of Public Health, Ben Gurion University of the Negev, Israel
526. Eva Revoyron, PhD candidate, agronomist, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France
527. Olivier Réchauchère, agronomist, French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE), Paris, France
528. Dr. Andreas Exner, ecologist and political scientist, RCE Graz-Styria, Center of Sustainable Social Transformation, University of Graz
529. Dr. Christina Plank, Institute for Development Research, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria

530. Prof. Markus Schermer, Department of Sociology, University of Innsbruck, Austria
531. Univ.-Prof. Christian Zeller, Department of Sociology and Social Geography,
University of Salzburg
532. Prof Emmanuel Frossard, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, ETH ZURICH
533. Dr Anant Jani, University of Heidelberg and University of Oxford
534. Dr. Friederike Habermann, economist & historian, Commons Institut, Germany
535. Dr Charlotte Spring, Laurier Centre for Sustainable Food Systems, Waterloo,
Canada
536. Dr. Miriam Boyer, Department of Agricultural Politics, Humboldt University, Berlin,
Germany
537. Prof. Dr. Johanna Jacobi, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, ETH Zürich
538. Jennifer Ramme, De-PI Literatur- und Kulturbeziehungen und Gender Studies,
Kulturwissenschaftliche Fakultät, Europa Universität Viadrina, Frankfurt/Oder,
Germany
539. Dr. Franck Galtier, CIRAD, France
540. Prof Niels Heine Kristensen, Department of People & Technology, Roskilde
University, Denmark
541. Prof. Dr. Aletta Bonn, Department Ecosystem Services Helmholtz-Centre for
Environmental Research – UFZ, Friedrich Schiller University Jena, German Centre
for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, Germany
542. Maha Tahiri, Adjunct professor at Tuft university and founder of Nutrition
Sustainability Strategies, USA
543. Erum Sattar, Lecturer and Program Director, Sustainable Water Management
program, Friedman School of Nutrition Science & Policy, Tufts University
544. Prof. Dr. Claudia Bieling, Dep. Societal Transition and Agriculture, Institute of Social
Sciences in Agriculture, University of Hohenheim, Germany
545. Dr. José Luis Vicente-Vicente. Environmental scientist, postdoctoral researcher in
agroecology and sustainable food systems, Leibniz Centre For Agricultural
Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg, Germany
546. Dr. Agnès Fargue-Lelièvre, agronomist, teacher/researcher, AgroParisTech, National
Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), UMR
SAD-APT, Paris-Grignon, France
547. Dr Alexandre Ribéron, associate professor, University of Toulouse III, Laboratoire
Evolution & Diversité Biologique, France
548. Prof.Dr.-Ing. Burkhard Ahlert, Food Technology and Microbiology, HS Fulda,
Germany
549. Dr. Birgit Hoinle, Dep. Societal Transition & Agriculture, University of Hohenheim
550. Prof. Hagai Levine, School of Public Health, Hebrew University-Hadassah,
Jerusalem, Israel
551. Karlotta Koch, PhD Candidate, Dep. Societal Transition and Agriculture, Institute of
Social Sciences in Agriculture, University of Hohenheim, Germany
552. Dr. Dorit Adler, President of the Israeli Forum for Sustainable Nutrition - IFSN
553. Dr. Lujain Alqodmani, Director of Global Action, EAT Foundation, Oslo, Norway
554. Dr. Bruno Mary, Research Director, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food
and the Environment (INRAE), UMR BioEcoAgro, Laon, France
555. Dr. Barbara Heinrich, researcher at Thünen Institute of Farm Economics, Germany
556. Dr. Nicolas Lampkin, researcher at Thünen Institute of Farm Economics, Germany
557. Daniel Tudela Staub, researcher at Thünen Institute of Farm Economics, Germany

558. Dr. Karin Geffert, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (LMU Munich) and Pettenkofer School of Public Health, Germany
559. Dr. Sigal Tepper, Nutritional Science, Tel-Hai College and the Israeli Forum for Sustainable Nutrition, Israel
560. Prof. Emeritus Luis S. Pereira, University of Lisbon, Portugal
561. Dr. Ofer Markman, GMCE life Science Hub and Shenkar Design Art Engineering, Israel
562. Dr. Harald Stelzer, University of Graz, research manager for the Field of Excellence Climate Change, Graz, Austria
563. Dr. Agnès Ducharne, CNRS Senior Scientist at Sorbonne Université (Paris, France), Académie d'Agriculture de France
564. Prof. Aron M. Troen, The School of Nutrition Sciences and Institute of Biochemistry, Food Science and Nutrition, The Robert. H. Smith Faculty of Agriculture, Food and Environment, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel
565. Noam Chehanovsky, PhD, Israeli forum for sustainable nutrition, Israel
566. Dr. Stefan Storcksdieck genannt Bonsmann, Max Rubner-Institut (MRI), Karlsruhe, Germany
567. Dr. Elke Brandes, Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute, Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries, Braunschweig, Germany
568. Maren Birkenstock, PhD Candidate, Thünen Institute of Rural Studies, Braunschweig, Germany
569. Jacob J. Bernhardt, PhD Candidate, Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute, Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries, Braunschweig, Germany
570. Dr. Kirstin Feussner, Georg-August-University Göttingen, Albrecht-von-Haller-Institute for Plant Sciences, Dept. of Plant Biochemistry, Göttingen, Germany
571. Lisa Eberbach, Thünen Institute of Rural Studies, Braunschweig, Germany
572. Tania Runge, Thünen Institute of Rural Studies, Braunschweig, Germany
573. Dr. Cornelia Herrfurth, Georg-August-University Göttingen, Albrecht-von-Haller-Institute for Plant Sciences, Dept. of Plant Biochemistry, Göttingen, Germany
574. Dr. Nicole Mathieu, CNRS, UMR LADYSS, Université Paris 1 Panthéon Sorbonne, Paris, France
575. PD Dr. Tuuli-Marja Kleiner, Thünen Institute of Rural Studies, Braunschweig, Germany
576. Lubana Al-Sayed, PhD Candidate, Dep. Societal Transition and Agriculture, Institute of Social Sciences in Agriculture, University of Hohenheim, Germany
577. Dr. Ana Contreras Navarro, School of Public Health, University College Cork, Ireland
578. Dr. Bartosz Bartkowski, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Department of Economics, Leipzig, Germany
579. Dr Gundi Knies, Thünen Institute of Rural Studies, Höxter, Germany
580. Prof. Emmanuel Corcket, Aix-Marseille University, Mediterranean Institute for Biodiversity and Ecology, Marseille, France
581. Pavlos Georgiadis, Research Associate, Dept. Societal Transition and Agriculture, Institute for Social Sciences in Agriculture, University of Hohenheim, Germany
582. Dr. Ruti Berger, Assuta Health Services Research Institute. Tel Aviv, Israel
583. Dr. Sarah Baum, Thünen Institute of Rural Studies, Braunschweig, Germany

584. Dr Sophie Gachet, Aix-Marseille University, Mediterranean Institute for Biodiversity and Ecology, Marseille, France
585. Natacha Sautereau, Organic Food and Farming Research Institute, ITAB, Avignon, France
586. Gabrielle Regula, Aix-Marseille University, CIVIS, IM2NP, France
587. Dr. Bruno Fady, senior scientist, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), URFM, Avignon, France
588. Prof. Evelyne Franquet, Aix-Marseille University, Mediterranean Institute for Biodiversity and Ecology, Marseille, France
589. Marc Benoit, Research Engineer, Université Clermont-Auvergne, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Clermont-Ferrand, France
590. Dr. Ioanna Mouratiadou, Assistant Professor, ISARA, Lyon, France and Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg, Germany
591. Pierre Triboulet, Research engineer, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Toulouse, France
592. Prof. Dr. Marcus Mergenthaler, Agricultural economics, South Westphalia University of Applied Sciences (SWUAS), Soest, Germany
593. Chantal Gascuel, senior scientist, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the environment (INRAE), UMR SAS, Rennes, France
594. Dr Hervé Jourdan, Research engineer, French National Research institute for Sustainable Development (IRD), Mediterranean Institute for Biodiversity and Ecology (IMBE), Nouméa, New Caledonia
595. MSc Patricia Scholz, Georg-August-University Göttingen, Albrecht-von-Haller-Institute for Plant Sciences, Dept. of Plant Biochemistry, Göttingen, Germany
596. Camille Salmon, PhD Candidate, AMAP lab, Montpellier University (UM), France
597. Dr Nelly Burle, Aix-Marseille University, dept of Physics, lab IM2NP, Marseille, France
598. Dr Nicolas Beaudoin, Research engineer (retired), National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), Laon, France
599. Dr. Friedrich-Karl Lücke, Professor (retired), Dept. Nutritional, Food & Consumer Sciences (OE), Fulda University of Applied Sciences, Germany
600. Dr. Thore Prien, Lecturer, Institute for Sociology/ Europa Universität Flensburg, Germany
601. Dr Errol Véla, Associate Professor, University of Montpellier, lab AMAP, France
602. Prof Gilles Brunschwig, VetAgro Sup, INRAE, Clermont-Auvergne University, Clermont-Ferrand, France
603. Prof. Gilles Belaud, G-Eau, Institut Agro Montpellier, France
604. Dr. Bernd Ulber, DNPW Agricultural Entomology, University of Göttingen, Germany
605. Dr. Guylain Grange, VetAgro Sup, Clermont-Ferrand, France
606. Dr. Monika Rut, ICLEI Europe, Freiburg
607. Dr Brigitte Talon, Lecturer, Aix-Marseille University, Mediterranean Institute for Biodiversity and Ecology, Marseille, France
608. Dr. Thomas Barth, Institute of Sociology, LMU Munich, Germany
609. Caroline Costongs, Director EuroHealthNet, the European Partnership for Health, Equity and Wellbeing, Brussels, Belgium

610. Prof. Dr. Stefan Heiland, Chair of Landscape Planning and Development, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
611. Dr. Chloé Maréchal, Laboratoire de Géologie de Lyon, Terre Planètes Environnement (LGL-TPE), Observatoire des Sciences de l'Univers de Lyon, Université Lyon 1, France
612. Dr. Pascal Maugis, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace, France
613. Dr. Vincent Perrier, Laboratoire de Géologie de Lyon, Terre Planètes Environnement (LGL-TPE), Observatoire des Sciences de l'Univers de Lyon, Université Lyon 1, France
614. Dr. Bastien Boussau, Laboratoire de Biométrie et Biologie Evolutive, CNRS, Université Lyon 1, France
615. Dr. Lena Schulte-Uebbing, Researcher, Environmental Systems Analysis Group, Wageningen University and Research, Wageningen, The Netherlands
616. Dr. Sébastien Levionnois, French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE), Paris, France
617. Dr. Leonith Hinojosa, French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE), Avignon, France
618. Dr. Verena Toussaint, Leibniz Center for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg, Germany
619. Prof. Dr. Harald Kächele, University of Sustainable Development (HNE), Eberswalde, Germany
620. Dr. Gilles Escarguel, Laboratoire d'Ecologie des Hydrosystèmes Naturels et Anthropisés, CNRS, Université Lyon 1, ENTPE, Villeurbanne, France
621. Dr. Jennifer L. Trilk, University of South Carolina School of Medicine Greenville, Greenville, South Carolina, USA
622. PD Dr. Heike Huebener, climatologist, University Giessen, Germany
623. MLA Dirk Wascher, SUSMETRO, Tilburg, Netherlands
624. Dr Franziska Matthies-Wiesler, Institute of Epidemiology, Helmholtz Zentrum München, Germany
625. Reed Cowden, researcher at PLEN, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
626. Dr Jérôme Enjalbert, researcher in genetics, INRAE, Génétique Quantitative et Evolution - Le Moulon, Université Paris-Saclay, Gif sur Yvette, France
627. Dr. Sophie Générmont, INRAE, France
628. Dr. Martin Sauber, Lecturer, Universität Hamburg, Germany
629. Alessandra Gerson Saltiel Schmidt, Institute of Advanced Architecture of Catalonia
630. Dr. Diana Sorg, Animal Scientist, German Environment Agency (UBA), Germany
631. Enrique Falceto de Barros, MD, FAM MED, MScEd, Universidade de Caxias do Sul, Brazil
632. Ozden Gokdemir, MD, PhD, Assoc Dr., Izmir University of Economics, Faculty of Medicine, Izmir, Turkey
633. Pr Fabrice Flipo, philosopher, Institut Mines-Télécom / Université de Paris Cité
634. Dr. Joey Allen, microbial ecologist, Université Rennes 1, France
635. Dr. Ellen Hornung, molecular biologist, University of Goettingen, Germany
636. Prof. Dr. Katja Tielbörger, Plant Ecologist, University of Tübingen, Germany
637. Ass Prof. Liz Hanna, RN, RCCN, BA, MPH, PhD, Australian National University. Chair Environmental Health - World Federation of Public Health Associations

638. Tatiana Souza de Camargo, biologist, PhD, Associate Professor - Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, member of the Planetary Health Study Group Brazil, Education Fellow in Planetary Health Alliance.
639. Dr Gunhild A. Stordalen, MD/PhD, Founder and Executive Chair, EAT
640. Dr. Andrei Dörre, Institute of Geographical Sciences, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
641. Dr. Rémi Cardinael, Soil scientist and agronomist, CIRAD
642. Prof. Dr. Lutz Breuer, Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany
643. Prof. Dr. Claas Nendel, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg, Germany
644. Dr. Carsten Paul, Environmental scientist, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg, Germany
645. Prof. Dr. Christoph Kohlmeyer, Raumplanung, TU Dortmund, Germany
646. Eva Rahner, M.A., Scientific Coordinator Leibniz Research Network Biodiversity, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Germany
647. Dr. Sibylle Schroer, Scientific Coordinator for Sustainability Research, Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, Germany
648. Hein van der Voort, Linguist, Museu Paraense Emílio Goeldi, Belém (PA), Brazil.
649. Dr. Guy Pe'er, Dept Ecosystem Services in 1) German Centre for integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig and 2) UFZ - Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Leipzig, Germany.
650. Dr. Santi Mañosa, Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.
651. Dr. Marta Goula. Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.
652. José Manuel Blanco Moreno, Departament de Biologia Evolutiva, Ecologia i Ciències Ambientals, Universitat de Barcelona, Spain.
653. Prof. Narcís Prat, Emeritus professor of Ecology, Universitat de Barcelona. Spain
654. Dr Jordi Pagès Fauria, Centre d'Estudis Avançats de Blanes (CEAB-CSIC), Spanish National Research Council. Spain.
655. Dr. Biel Obrador. Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.
656. Dra Creu Palacín. Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.
657. Dr Humbert Salvadó Cabré, Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences. University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain
658. 659. Dr Michael James Roast. Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences. University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain
659. Dr. Mario Díaz, Department of Biogeography and Global Change, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, CSIC, Madrid, Spain
660. Dr Enric Batllori Presas, Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences. University of Barcelona, Spain.
661. Dr. Yanka Kazakova-Mateva, Associate Professor, Economics of Natural Resources Department, University of National and World Economy, Sofia
662. Dr. Ana Sanz Pérez, Postdoc researcher. Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.
663. Prof Carolina Sampera, Researcher Animal Biology, University of Barcelona, Spain

664. Assoc. Prof. Marina Angelova Nikolova, PhD, Department "Agrarian Economics", D. A. Tsenov Academy of Economics, Svishtov, Bulgaria.
665. Dr. David Serrano, Department of Conservation Biology, Estación Biológica de Doñana, CSIC, Seville, Spain.
666. Dr. Juan Traba. Department of Ecology. Universidad Autónoma de Madrid.
667. Dr. Cornelia Krug, Department of Evolutionary Biology and Environmental Studies, University of Zurich, Switzerland
668. Prof. Marianne Penker, Department of Economics and Social Sciences, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria.